

Supporting Information

Effects of Loading and Nafion Content on the Activity and Stability of Iridium Oxygen Evolution Reaction Catalysts

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Figure S1. Tafel plots of metallic Ir as a function of loading, derived from LSVs shown in Figure 1a and measured by SFC.

Figure S2. a) Total anodic charge (ECSA) of metallic Ir, integrated from Figure 1a over the 0.4 – 1.4 V_{RHE} range and normalized by the total Ir mass in the sample. b) Applied current density during galvanostatic hold, normalized by Ir mass (left) and ECSA (right). All measurements were done by the SFC.

Figure S3. Applied current density during galvanostatic hold of metallic Ir, normalized by Ir mass (left) and ECSA (right), plotted against Ir dissolution normalized by surface area a) and by Ir mass b). c) Potential measured and d) Overpotential at the end of the galvanostatic hold as a function of Ir loading. All measurements were done by the SFC.

Figure S4. Influence of Ir loading on OER activity and electrochemistry of metallic Ir. a), b) and c) CVs ($0.4 - 1.4 V_{\text{RHE}}$, 50 mV s^{-1} , 4 cycles). d), e) and f) LSVs ($1.2 - 1.55 V_{\text{RHE}}$, 10 mV s^{-1}). a), b) are

normalized by surface area, c), d) by Ir mass, and e), f) by total anodic charge. All data were measured using RDE at 1600 RPM.

Figure S5. a) Total anodic charge (ECSA) of metallic Ir, integrated from Figure S4a over the 0.4–1.4 V_{RHE} range and normalized by the total Ir mass in the sample. b) Potential measured and c) Overpotential at the end of the galvanostatic hold as a function of Ir loading. d) Integrated dissolution profiles during a 5 mA cm^{-2} hold. e) Percentage activity loss, normalized by surface area (left) and ECSA (middle), percentage ECSA loss (right). Activity and ECSA loss were estimated from LSVs (at 1.6 V_{RHE}) and CVs, respectively, before and after the 5 mA cm^{-2} hold. All data were measured using RDE at 1600 RPM.

Figure S6. Influence of drop-casting procedure on metallic Ir OER activity. a) CVs (0.4 – 1.4 V_{RHE} , 50 mV s^{-1} , 4 cycles). b) LSVs (1.2 – 1.6 V_{RHE} , 10 mV s^{-1}). All measurements are done using RDE at 1600 RPM.

Figure S7. a) Ir ECSA integrated from Figure 2a over the 0.4–1.4 V_{RHE} range and normalized by the total metallic Ir mass in the sample. b) Potentials measured during applied 5 mA cm^{-2} hold. c) Applied current density during galvanostatic hold, normalized by Ir ECSA for various Nafion contents. All measurements were done by the SFC.

Figure S8. Applied current density during galvanostatic hold of metallic Ir normalized by ECSA, plotted against Ir dissolution normalized by surface area, measured using the SFC.

Figure S9. Influence of Nafion content on OER activity and electrochemistry of metallic Ir as measured by RDE. a), b) and c) CVs ($0.4 - 1.4 V_{\text{RHE}}$, 50 mV s^{-1} , 4 cycles). d), e) and f) LSVs ($1.2 - 1.6 V_{\text{RHE}}$, 10 mV s^{-1}). a), b) are normalized by surface area, c), d) by Ir mass, and e), f) by total anodic charge.

Figure S10. a) Total anodic charge (ECOA) of metallic Ir, integrated from Figure S9a over the 0.4–1.4 V_{RHE} range and normalized by the total Ir mass in the sample. b) Potential measured and c) Integrated dissolution profiles during a 5 mA cm^{-2} hold. d) Percentage activity loss, normalized by surface area (left) and ECSA (middle), percentage ECSA loss (right). Activity and ECSA loss were estimated from LSVs (at 1.6 V_{RHE}) and CVs, respectively, before and after the 5 mA cm^{-2} hold. All data were measured using RDE.

Figure S11. Effect of Nafion application method on metallic Ir in RDE: mixed into ink vs. post-deposition drop-cast.

Figure S12. a) ECSA of IrO₂ integrated from Figure 3a over the 0.4–1.4 V_{RHE} range and normalized by the total Ir mass in the sample. b) Potential measured during galvanostatic hold of IrO_x and b) Applied current density normalized by Ir ECSA, plotted against Ir dissolution normalized by surface area a) and by Ir mass. All measurements were done by the SFC.

Figure S13. SEM images of IrO₂ at the low and high magnifications as a function of Nafion content.

Figure S14. SEM images of metallic Ir at the low and high magnifications as a function of Nafion content.

Figure S15. SEM images showing the coffee-ring effect in IrO₂ (top) and metallic Ir (bottom) as a function of Nafion content. Original images were processed in ImageJ using a yellow inverted lookup table and contrast enhancement to improve ring visibility.

Figure S16. High-magnification SEM images of coffee-ring effect in metallic Ir films as a function of Nafion content.

Figure S17. SEM-EDX mapping (left) and EDX spectra (right) of IrO₂ as a function of Nafion content.

Figure S18. SEM-EDX mapping (left) and EDX spectra (right) of metallic Ir as a function of Nafion content.

Figure S19. XPS spectra of Ir 4f, F 1s, O 1s, and C 1s for a) metallic Ir and b) IrO₂ as a function of Nafion content.

Figure S20. Representative Ir 4f XPS fitting for Ir/F and Ir³⁺/Ir⁴⁺ ratio calculations, shown for metallic Ir and IrO₂ samples with 40 % Nafion. C 1s and O 1s fits are included for IrO₂ with 40 % Nafion, and the same fitting procedure was applied to all samples.

Figure S21. CF_x/Ir (left) and O-CF₂/Ir (right) ratios calculated from XPS spectra for IrO₂ and metallic Ir samples as a function of Nafion content.

Figure S22. Near-surface Ir oxidation-state fractions (Ir 4f XPS) as a function of Nafion content. Left: IrO₂ (Ir³⁺ fraction), right: Ir black (Ir⁰/Ir³⁺/Ir⁴⁺ fractions).

Figure S23. X-ray diffraction patterns of Ir black and IrO₂ powders (as-received) and IrO₂ after calcination at 600 °C for 12 h. Reference Bragg peak positions for fcc Ir (♦) and rutile IrO₂ (★) are marked above the patterns.

Figure S24. Contact angles of metallic Ir (top) and IrO₂ (bottom) as a function of Nafion content in the samples.